

Large-grain somaclonal variants in IR26

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We have been researching ways to improve restorer lines by using somaclonal variation to better exploit rice heterosis. A series of somaclonal variants with useful characteristics have been obtained. One is the large-grain variants from IR26, which once was an important restorer in the hybrid rice area in the Yangtse Valley of China.

The IR26 large-grain variants have different plant heights and growth durations. They were obtained by culturing immature panicles as explants and selecting from the R₂. These variants are now in the R₇ generation.

Two of the variants (variant-35 and variant-41) are superior to IR26 in 1,000-grain weight and grains/panicle (see table). These increases were to some extent at the expense of fertility. Grain weight/plant of the variants, which was an average of 10 randomly sampled plants, was higher than that of IR26.

Chromosome observation of root tip and pollen mother cell of the variants showed no change in chromosome number. However, peroxidase isozyme analysis showed a different electrophoretic pattern between variants and the parent. The two variants have one more band than the parent. The variants and the parent also had stoichiometrical differences in some bands.

To identify the usefulness of these variants as restorers, they were crossed with Zhenshan 97 A. We compared the performance of the F₁ hybrids of Zhenshan 97 A/Variant 41 with that of Zhenshan 97 A/Milyang 46, a leading local hybrid. Zhenshan 97 A/Variant 41 performed better than the check. The large grain characteristic of the variant was expressed in the F₁.

These large-grain variants can be used in hybrid rice breeding programs. ■

Performance of IR26 large-grain somaclonal variants.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicles/plant (no.)	Spikelets/panicle (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)	Fertility (%)	1000-grain weight (g)	Grain weight (g/plant)	Days to heading
IR26	88.4	12.5	97.5	90.3	92.6	25.7	26.8	80
Variety 41	96.2	11.7	138.4	97.3	70.5	41.3	40.3	85
Variety 35	87.9	13.7	120.5	91.5	75.8	35.7	38.6	79
Zhenshan 97 A/ Milyang 46	89.2	16.1	112.4	92.9	82.8	27.6	32.7	82
Zhenshan 97 A/ Variety 41	101.4	14.3	161.1	118.7	73.7	30.8	45.7	81

Physiological traits of selected maintainers in hybrid rice breeding

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Identifying physiologically elite maintainers may help in their conversion to effective cytoplasmic male sterile lines through backcrossing programs.

We studied photosynthetic rate, dry matter production, and yield of 21

effective maintainers from IRRI during the 1990 wet season under field conditions where 60 kg N/ha was applied. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Seedlings were transplanted in the main field in 3-m² plots, spaced at 15 × 10 cm. We took samples to assess leaf area index (LAI) at flowering, and total dry matter (TDM) at 35 d, flowering, and harvest. Photosynthetic rate was measured on flag leaves with the LI-6000 Photosynthesis

Physiological traits of selected maintainers from IRRI, CRRI, Cuttack, India, 1990 wet season.

Maintainer	Flowering		Total dry matter (g/m ²)				Yield (g/m ²)	HI (%)
	Photosynthetic rate (mg CO ₂ /dm ² per h)	SLW (mg/dm ²)	LAI	35 d	Flowering	Harvest		
V20 B	36.2	324	2.18	123	355	698	284	40
Ai-Nan-Tsao	35.2	317	1.78	118	350	477	201	42
Sernaingincha 61-54	44.7	410	3.56	141	570	753	355	47
IR10176-2-4-6-2	44.8	434	2.17	175	381	580	195	34
IR19723-2-2-1	40.2	424	2.89	164	552	860	335	39
IR19728-9-2-2-3-3	37.3	379	1.58	170	396	850	276	32
IR19728-9-32-3-3	40.4	389	3.11	128	542	813	373	46
IR19743-40-3-2-3	33.8	347	2.20	145	332	825	377	46
IR19774-8-3-1-1	39.3	377	2.78	119	428	772	348	45
IR19774-23-2-1-3	43.3	406	2.15	143	387	760	379	49
IR19791-8-3-2	42.0	383	2.51	135	453	790	370	46
IR19791-12-1-2-2-2	48.3	425	2.04	235	433	767	340	44
IR19805-12-1-3-1-2	41.1	412	2.00	145	334	753	291	39
IR19806-8-1-3-2	46.3	423	3.38	184	438	771	300	39
IR19816-8-1-3-2	47.1	432	2.03	124	381	880	428	48
IR19819-31-2-3-1-1	38.2	378	3.05	106	473	758	347	45
IR19891-12-3-2-1	47.7	416	2.14	137	413	650	279	43
IR22107-120-1	38.4	350	3.06	221	484	1012	466	46
IR28138-43-3-1-3-2	44.2	393	2.17	135	473	866	336	38
IR28142-6-3-2-2-2	47.1	444	2.55	133	474	933	448	48
IR33955-8-1-1	30.4	396	3.19	130	487	1083	485	45
Mean	41.2	393	2.50	148	435	793	339	43
LSD (0.05)	4.3	38	0.21	18	80	23	25	-